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w\ p\ a\ e\ y\ q\ f; c\ h\ u\ v\ maom t&srw\Bud\ \ a\ u\ s\ m\ u\ e\ f; u\ l\ y\ IP\ ; Bud\ u\ v\ u\ D\ g; jz\ i\ h\ t\ m; u\ e\ f; u\ l\ & m t&srw\Bud\ on\ p\ w\ i\ q\ a' g\ o\ x\ u\ & e\ r\ q\ k\ m; b\ d\ j\ y\ e\ p\ m\ i\ f; i\ y\ i\ r\ M\ u\ n\ h\ a\ c\ / onfcjci f w\ m\ r\ n\ y\ d\ < u\ l\ r\ w\ l\ f\ q\ u\ k\ u\ o\ d; aom y\ IP\ ; r\ n\ r\ c\ h\ & y\ E\ l\ b\ a\ t\ m\ i\ f\ y\ a\ v\ m\ i\ v\ s\ u\ f\ t&srw\ \ onfcjci f *IP& n\ ES h\ t\ x\ i\ j\ n\ p\ h\ u\ l\ t\ b\ i\ a\ e\ on/ x\ h\ e\ m\ u\ f\ t&srw\ Bud\ u\ l\ rrdt m; onfcjci f y\ g & e\ ES h\ t\ r\ b\ o\ l\ q\ f; c\ h\ u\ y\ g & e\ f\ a\ v\ u\ x\ m; \ / t&srw\Bud\ on\ y\ IP\ ; t\ m; t\ j\ c\ m; olw\ \ u\ ES\ u\ r\ n\ h\ t\ a\ l\ Mumi f\ o\ b\ jz\ i\ h\ x\ b; r\ a\ 0; ap&ef y\ IP\ ; \ v\ u\ b\ l\ o\ y\ w\ l\ u\ l\ ay; i\ a\ e\ m\ u\ b\ a\ w\ m\ y\ g; r\ s\ v\ l\ u\ a\ p\ on/ q\ f; u\ p\ h\ y\ a\ o\ m\ t\ r\ r\ s\ x\ u\ k\ u\ & m\ u\ v\ n\ f; o\ y\ w\ v\ a\ y; i\ a\ u\ s\ m\ i\ f; x\ d\ v\ l\ u\ y\ g\ a\ p\ j\ c\ i\ f\ jz\ i\ h\ rrdt m; & e\ f\ y\ k\ m\ o\ l\ y\ IP\ ; t\ m; t\ o\ u\ b\ a\ b; r\ s\ v\ w\ l\ u\ i\ f\ a\ p\ & e\ f\ u, q, f\ a\ y; aom r\ a\ x\ & j\ r\ w\ Bud\ \ onfcjci f w\ *IP& n\ r\ n\ O\ b\ w\ i\ b\ a\ v\ m\ u\ l\ p\ & m\ jz\ p\ l\ y\ g\ on/

6/ tjc m *P&n rsn

t&srw\Bud\ on\ i\ az\ n\ j\ y\ c\ h\ y\ a\ o\ m\ M\ u\ n\ h\ i\ z\ G\ & m\ *IP& n\ w\ l\ b\ m\ r\ u\ t\ j\ c\ m; aom *IP& n\ r\ s\ n; r\ s\ n; p\ h\ & y\ g\ a\ o; on/ , i\ f\ w\ l\ t\ e\ u\ r\ s\ t\ c\ s\ a\ o\ m\ *IP& n\ w\ l\ u\ l\ M\ u\ n\ h\ i\ z\ G\ & m\ a\ v\ l\ w\ m\ w\ i\ j\ y\ o\ n; y\ g\ r\ n/

(u) q&mt m 1/2 oav; pmjci f *P&n f

r\ a\ x\ & j\ r\ w\ Bud\ on\ o\ k\ a\ v\ m\ u\ x\ w\ x\ m; j\ r\ w\ p\ h\ b\ & s\ f\ u\ b\ m\ r\ u\ rrdt m; jz\ p\ c\ i\ z\ a\ o\ m\ t&srw\Bud\ \ o\ Z\ r\ a\ x\ & f\ u\ l\ y\ i\ f\ t\ v\ e\ f; h\ o\ a\ v; p\ m; aom r\ a\ x\ & j\ r\ w\ Bud\ \ jz\ p\ on/ t&srw\Bud\ \ o\ Z\ r\ a\ x\ & f\ t\ m; b, f\ t\ c\ g\ r\ s\ r\ a\ r\ b\ jz\ i\ h\ t&srw\Bud\ \ o\ Z\ r\ a\ x\ & f\ & b\ n\ i\ [k\ M\ u\ m; aom t& y\ o\ l\ r\ s\ u\ E\ n\ r\ i\ v\ u\ f\ t\ y\ c\ b\ j\ r\ s\ u\ l\ y\ d\ & e\ f; w\ l\ r\ u\ t&srw\Bud\ \ o\ m\ o\ l\ O\ b\ a\ c\ j\ i\ f\ j\ y\ k\ v\ s\ u\ l\ u\ s\ e\ f; p\ u\ b\ a\ w\ m\ r\ y\ g\ on/ (olw\ e\ d\ |? ' R 62/ ty? |? y? 165/)

(c) rdtm qhrrnqlygvfi t&g ra&gvucvluemwwjci*P&ni

t&sjrwbuðoni q&mtay: ½hojrwEhwwlyð wpyg;olwltm; qhr
wwl/ztu rdtm; qhrrnqlygvfi t&g ra&g vucif vluemwwaom
obawmaumif t&sjrwbuðvntjzplygon/ wpaelwfi t&sjrwftm; Oyzln, f
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clepEþft&g jzpaom , ae& [efjy/aom omraPi, lubhomoN tqhtrud
vfi Oðxyjzi h gcfñ (yg&m, e? 38/) [k qhronful em, lvg bamumif Munññ
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(*) oytj, rðvap&ef qijci qefbðfay;awmrjci*P&ni

t&sjrwbuðoni qefbðfay; & mü oytj, rðvap&ef rpi lu, haomtpm?
roi haomtpmrsm; ul vñOa&ñi fuðawmrñcygon/ (yg&m, e? 39/) xbl tpmul
qijci pm; oñ awmrñcygon & [efjzponrñpi y&eAhepñonwñ h atmi f avcsOf
wufci? Buñxñjci f rvOf r&eñy/ xltjyif 44 Og ywvñ tñarð i lursOfci f
vnfr&eñy/ Oðd tm; ul pluxkw&ygaom aumcsvavsmif tñpufci f rjy&onh
ebZf'kwif ul Eþi 30 wñ f tm; xkwðñ; awmrñcygon/ ('ð |? 2? 328/ 'ð |? 3? 329/)
wpyg; wñf zvormywf Oipm; ae wwloblyif qefchuaomtçü
qef; avmif owl tustbuðrm; ap&ef eð&m" ormywul Oipm; awmrñcygon/
(r? 3? 278/ r? |? 4? 193/)

(C) a'opm&ð&ðwfi aemufsvluif apmi h&ñucsjrñhwjci*P&ni

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rsm; ul cñfompñvluifgEñ h& ; twul ul lwl apmi h&ñucsjrñhwjci vluifgavh
& bñfñ t&sjrwbuð \ *P&ni wptcyijzponi/ xbl apmi h&ñu&it vluifg
& ojzi h aemufuñ tñy&mae&mr&on&ñom tjc; & [efwul iñhaomtm; jzi h
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(i) oytjEþPEsh tui f r&ñjnpñhwjci*P&ni

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wptk vfi wp&ubomñ; í pm; oñ&rñi [k ynawmrñcygon/ t&sjrwbuðoni
a'opm&ðuc&m xñ@yfta&muñwfi emruet; ojzi h rjyeEñ Bm yxr&uñsvñ
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allumi f jyeñ ynway; awmrñcygon/ (& wemñ P&ni? 130-131/) t*kw&edum, f
tm, mpe0*kwfi jrwþñb&m; u & [efwltm; jyi f xeðomqE "mvawmrñsm;
jzpaom; atmi f Eñqñwif ññjy&mü] cpom; wñ , Munññom& [ef; onf qlawmi f
vlygvfi t&sj bñ&d ykv&mi? t&sj arm*ðmeñwubljzpaomif qlawmi f lu? olwñ

u&lji? txi&o:jci&fsm; rjy&vly&E&f jz&pon/ , ifr&n t&S&f&rw&Bu&D\ Mun&f&n
z&G &m*P&n&w&p&cl&y&fz&p&M&umi&f o&E&f&y&gon/ x&ly&f ruse&f&maom &[e&f&o&C&m&w&f
&ly&guv&n&f jy&f&p&pmi&h&&n&u&ay&jci&f v<&y&on&fsm; u&ll p&D&H&a&qmi &E&u&ay&jci&f w&u&ll Mun&f&ci&f
jzi&h&o&w&i&f&f&h&az&m&v&u&ll&c&f&aj&r&f&u&f&ci&f o*E [*P&E&S&f&j&y&n&f&M&umi&f&v&n&f o&E&f&y&gon/

]7) E&f&om; t&G& f&S&fi , fuav;\ ou&E&f&E&f&y&w&bou&f q&H&a&om&p&um; u&ll em, l&v&su&f
jy&f&y&i&on&fu&ll Mun&f&ci&f&t&m; jzi&h&a&om&O&p&ó w*P&n&E&S&f&v&n&f j&y&n&f&M&umi&f o&E&f&y&gon/
q&m&&mt&&y&bo&ll &n&f&ar&on&f O&D&ac&g&i&x&m; jci&f? y&e&A&h&ep&h&on&x&d E&f&ay&g&i&f (30)w&ll&f&w&ll&f
t&y&R&mae&&mr&sm;ü a&us&mr&ci&f? r&t&y&p&u&a&om e&b&Z&Z&w&i&fu&ll u&si&h&aw&mr&f&cl&on&h&t&S&f&rw&Bu&D\
*P&n&w&f&f&n Mun&f&n&f r&O&E&f&h&t&mi&f&i&f&&y&gon/

x&lu&b&h&om t&S&f&rw&Bu&D\ t&x&t&x&f&sm; v&f&h&a&om *P&n&w&f&teu&f y&e&A&h&ef
p&h&g&e&D&t&c&e&f&w&f jy&k&usi&cl&on&h p&f&f&a&qmi&t&su&f*P&n&f&n t&x&t&j&cm; q&H&E&S&h Mun&f&n&z&G &m
ta&umi&f&q&ly&i&f&jz&p&y&gon/ &[E&h (7)y&g; w&ll r&ci&f&z&p&a&om om&D&ya&P&or&Bu&D&on&f r&p&ar' d&d
t, f&sm; u&ll v&u&t&h&cm; ol&w&p&D&jz&p&on/ t&S&f&rw&Bu&D&on&f r&id&em&u&f&q&ll y&e&A&h&ef p&h&g&e&D
t&c&e&f&ol&h&mu&a&omf r&id&ar&f&z&f&h& &mw&v&u&f&e&f&oll ta&m&u&f&y&e&f&v&su&f r&ci&Bu&D&u&ll u&ll&f&w&ll&f
w&m; jy&v&su&f a&om&v&my&e&f&v&n&ap&jci&f&jzi&h r&b*P&a&us&Z&f&u&ll t&x&t&od ta&ll&u&q&y&aw&mr&f&ch
y&gon/ , if&u&ll&t&w&k& li av&mu&v&lo&m; w&ll&t&ae&jzi&h r&id&v&av&mu&t&w&f&f a&m&u&a&t&mi&f
y&h&a&qmi&f&y&f&ga&om r&b&w&ll& aus&Z&f*P&f&te&E&u&ll q&y&i&f rule&f[k&q&h&e&½&h&E&S&f&f&ly&D&ol ou&E&f&S
xi&f&n; r&br&sm; u&ll av&mu&h&v&mu&k&v&f&t&u&f&w&m; r&sm; w&ly&f&h&at&mi&f w&ll&u&w&e&f &E&u&a&qmi&f
ay&jci&f&E&S&h&rs&u&f&G& f&y&ly&f&a&om r&br&sm; u&ll&n&f a&m&u&f&mb&O&r&S& r&id&v&ly&f&y&kor&O& u&ll&v&f&tr&l
r&e&f&or&u&ll&om" h&c: E&h &f&a&umi&f&r&jy&ly&D&w&ll&f t&r&O&ajci&f&r&f&f&sm; r&ar&h&av&sm&h&jy&f&ay&oi&f&y&gon/

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E&S&f&h&om; on&f y&r&m&E&h&f&jy&&y&g&v&f&f O&g; ½&ly&i&f&ri&f&ri&f&Bu&D&rs&m; E&S&f&y&i&f w&ly&gon/ O&g; ½&ly&i&f&sm; on&f
j&ri&h&av&av at&mu&b&ob&my&f&f&h&v&u&ll&f&av&av jz&p&ou&ub&ll t&S&f&rw&Bu&D\ E&h&f&e&sa&om
p&w&f&x&m; on&f&n&f Mun&f&n&z&G &m jz&p&on/ x&lu&b&h&om t&S&f&rw&Bu&D\ *P&n&f&sm; u&ll
z&w&½&av&h&v&Mun&f&n&½&f&Oru v&lu&em&usi&f&h&ci&f&t&m; jzi&h&av&mu&h&v&mu&k&v&f&t&a&&E&S&h&j&y&n&f&h
ly&D&aj&r&mu&E&h&f&M&umi&f o&E&f&y&gon/ ae&p&O&f&i&f&q&ll&h&aj&z&S&f&ae&&a&om y&n&ma&&? p&D&y&f&h&a&&? v&r&h&a&&E&S&h
p&m; O&w&f&ea&& [h&om ta&&u&p&f&sm; u&ll&n&f a&jy&v&n&f&h& aj&z&S&f&E&h&f&n&jz&p&on/ b&&m;? w&&m;?
o&f&C&m& pon&h &w&em(3)y&g;\ *P&a&us&Z&f&om&ru v&u&D&D&q&m&jz&p&a&om r&b&E&S&h&ue&ll&u&ll
v&u&f&h&f&g&f&t&jz&p&f&i , p&O&aw&mi&f&aus&u&av; b&O&r&f&i t&G&f&f&r&e&f&f&u& aw&Bu&ko&i&M&um; c&G&h
&on&h oi&f&g&f&m&j&ri&f&g&f&M&um; q&f&mv&n&f [h&om r&id&t&ay&: aus&Z&f&jy&f&cl&z&f&on&h q&f&mv&ll&N
*P&a&us&Z&f&u&ll ten&f&i , f&ly&f&jz&p&ly&gap jy&e&f&v&n&b&v&w&f&t&all&u&q&y&f&w&f&on&f&or&sm; jz&p&ap&e&f
&n&f&e&f&i w&i&f&y&v&u&f&y&g&aw&mi&on/

ur̥ul̥p̥m̥i̥f̥

ygVdwn̥r̥sm̥ (q|o*ŋv̥t̥)

t|u e0u 'ou {um'oueŋgvygVd

Oy&ŋPñoygVd

cġūyġ "r̥ŋ" 0'ge Ew0lv̥i̥ olv̥eŋgvygVd

ZmvuygM(yXarm bma*g)

ZmvuygM('kv̥d̥, m bma*g)

ax&*gxmygVd

0ē, r[̥n0*ŋgVd

t|uxmr̥sm̥

t|omv̥ēit|uxm' (1957)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

ty'get|uxm' (1959)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

Oy&ŋPño|uxm' (1957)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

Oy&ŋPñt|uxm' (1962)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

Zmvu|uxm' (1962)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

ax&*gxmt|uxm' (1959)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

'ĊeLm, r[̥n0*ŋt|uxm' (1959)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

"r̥ŋ"|uxm (yXarm bma*g)/ (1962)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

ygxū0*ŋuxm' (1957)/)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

oġ lv̥d̥uxm ('kv̥d̥ t|ŋŋ)/ (1957)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

olv̥eŋgVw|uxm ('kv̥d̥, m bma*g)/ (1958)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme/

tax̥x̥ŋsr̥sm̥

Phys Davids (T.W). (1966). *Pali-English Dictionary*. London: Pali Text Society London.

pEtr̥m (t&ŋŋ)/ (1992)/ "r̥ŋ" 0wlv̥w̥m̥L̥ŋŋ (yxr̥w̥ŋ)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme yEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

pEtr̥m (t&ŋŋ)/ (1992)/ "r̥ŋ" 0wlv̥w̥m̥L̥ŋŋ ('kv̥d̥ w̥ŋ)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme yEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

pEtr̥m (t&ŋŋ)/ (1992)/ "r̥ŋ" 0wlv̥w̥m̥L̥ŋŋ (ww̥d̥ w̥ŋ)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme yEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

pEtr̥m (t&ŋŋ)/ (1992)/ "r̥ŋ" 0wlv̥w̥m̥L̥ŋŋ (yġr̥w̥ŋ)/ &efuletr̥ŋ omoema&;0p̥p̥Xme yEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

Zeumb0kb (t&ŋŋ)/ (2006)/ &went̥P&ŋŋ/ &efuletr̥ŋ e, lb̥m̥;rm̥;at̥n̥z̥ŋqu̥yEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

ax̥;v̥l̥f̥(0b̥) ("r̥m̥p̥&d̥)/ (1994)/ &wemoŋygaus̥Zġ/ &efuletr̥ŋ ae&&ŋyEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

x̥ēŋjri̥h̥(0b̥)/ (1968)/ ygVbu̥h̥0g[̥n̥&t̥b̥d̥m̥eŋ/ &efuletr̥ŋ w̥u̥i̥0k̥ŋr̥sm̥;yEŋŋw̥L̥ŋŋ/

- jrefmEi fi AR ömoentzW (1963)/ *ax&my'gefvg/vvnmf* jrefmijye! (yxrtly!)/ &efulefrW jrefmEi fi H
AR ömoentzByEgywLwLw
- Oplwöm&mbOb (Ob)/ (1972)/ *EfiHwnAR ömoer[nAR OiP* (wwd w!)/ &efulefrW AR ömoentz
tzyEgywLwLw
- Oplwöm&mbOb (Ob)/ (1972)/ *EfiHwnAR ömoer[nAR OiP* (t|rw&yxryit!)/ &efulefrW
AR ömoentzByEgywLwLw
- ObOb (t&S!)/ (1963)/ *yg&m, eOwK* &efulefrW [kmOwByEgywLwLw
- [kwpef (Ob)/ (1951)/ *y'wrIkom[hom ygvjrefmt bñmf* &efulefrW crf,oma&mi plkyEgywLwLw
- tñrmif (Ob)/ (1994)/ *AR bmonaumi/vph, mu!* &efulefrW omoemawmf&ef,um; jyelyfr;a&;
ObpXmeyEgywLwLw